

ARTISTIC INTERPRETATION OF WOMAN'S FATE IN THE WORKS OF
MALALA YOUSAFZAI

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ABSTRACT In the world literature, the importance of the works that are directly related to the fate of women, their lifestyle, experiences, and mentality is incomparable and always received with great interest. Examples of high creativity created by Malala Yousafzai are among them and have a strong place in this regard. These works, which were met with great recognition and applause by the readers, describe in detail the violation of women's rights, the restriction of their freedom, and the fact that women and men are seen as representatives of different classes in society. And it is mentioned that separate laws are developed for each of the representatives of these two genes, and on the basis of these laws, women face many pressures and face great difficulties.

Key words: education, upbringing, knowledge, science, family, woman, women's rights, gender equality.

Introduction:

Malala Yousafzai is recognized as one of the famous writers of our time, who has a sharp pen, deep thoughts, a rich world view, and is one of the great creators. When asked why her work is different, it is because in her work, the position of a woman in social life, her perspective, her spiritual world, and her feelings are depicted on the basis of specific images. Despite her young age, she has achieved great achievements in fulfilling her duties to the country and has achieved many achievements. In particular, not only in her country, but throughout the world, she has been making great efforts to protect women's rights, for their education, to create all the conditions and freedoms for them, and these efforts are bearing fruit. To date, Malala, who has been awarded numerous state awards, remains the youngest Nobel laureate.

Materials and Methods:

The prose of women, who discovered the wonderful possibilities of determining their position in the literature of the 20th century, began to develop rapidly. The prose, which describes ordinary life events and a dull lifestyle in the past, expressed her in "another reality" and informed how a woman feels about the world. Such a worldview aroused great interest in literature. The

image of a woman, revealing her inner experiences, depicting her external appearance, depicting her social status as a person, is considered a relevant topic for all artists who lived in every era, and it is a very interesting topic for every reader.

Results and discussion:

Malala Yousafzai's work "I am Malala" is important in fiction because it deals with the role of women in the family and society, their problems and desires as human beings.

Especially the fact that her experiences are published in a book and this book is called "I am Malala" is proof once again that women have equal rights with men in society and that they have the right to education.

The fact that the work includes real life events, mainly the life paths of Malala, the author of the book, doubles the interest in this book.

The book, which starts with "I come from a country that was created at midnight", mainly tells about the general exclusion of girls from education. This book mainly tells about Malala herself, the people around her, her relatives, her friends who go to school with her, and the difficulties she faced during her education. Malala's school is owned by her father Ziauddin Yousafzai, and it is also about the founding of the school, the start of a partnership and ultimately the destruction of the sacred bond of friendship. The unprecedented difficulties in establishing the school, the bitter truths about the open corruption of higher organizations, and despite all these difficulties, father Ziauddin's determination to fight to the end are recorded. Her father, Ziauddin, is one of those people who fall down and get up without anyone's help and continue to fight. Since there was no support from her grandfather Rahul Amin, her father was determined to solve his problems on her own, which meant that he had to juggle her school activities along with providing for her family. And we can witness in the process of reading the book that her efforts in this direction were not easy.

It is a laborious and painstaking job to search for a place for a school building day and night, to pay two months' rent in advance, to collect documents, and to go door-to-door explaining to parents about this school. At the same time, it is a very good and meritorious work in the way of raising children's knowledge and expanding their world view!

The saddest thing is that parents don't understand what a modern school is, they don't fully understand what secular sciences are, they prefer free madrassas where they only memorize the Koran without understanding it and repeat it from morning to night without moving.

Fathers went to distant towns and villages to work, earn money, and support the family. Mothers did not know how to read and write, were illiterate, and most of them had no desire to learn.

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It required great heroism to establish a school in a remote place where such views, assumptions, and concepts prevailed.

It won't be difficult for the reader to understand how much work, patience, and a lot of money was spent to make all of these.

Malala went to school from a young age. Although her mother was illiterate, her father valued science very much. Malala's father often repeated that "the most beautiful sight in the world is the children going to school in uniform in the morning."

Malala herself was growing up as a girl with a thirst for knowledge. The fact that she learned all subjects with equal interest made her parents even happier. In this regard, the contributions of her friends Aisha, Moniba and Malka-i-Nur are invaluable. Because there was an atmosphere of healthy competition among friends, who studied for each other, waited impatiently for the results of the exams, and at the same time, they respected each other's knowledge and themselves as individuals. But it was not easy for the girls. Because the fate of girls born to illiterate mothers should be the same as theirs, the reason is that the girl child is brought up by the mother, and every day she says to her daughters, "You are going to study, your duty is to learn to cook, prepare sweet dishes for your future husband and to give birth to children, it's better to get ready to go to school early in the morning" was a sign that they should fulfill these tasks as well. The same fate awaited Malala. However, a loving and caring father supported him in every aspect. She always said to her daughter, "Malala, be free like a bird!" Walk in the ocean of your dreams without breaking your dreams. I will always protect you." Malala began to move towards her dreams thanks to her father's urgings to move forward. However, these successes were not easily achieved.

Conclusion.

Malala Yousafzai's work "I am Malala" repeatedly emphasizes that every woman in society has the right to be happy, to live freely and freely. Everyone should have a job they like, a profession they want, and a happy family. A woman is a part of society. As soon as a girl comes into this bright world, the desire to play with a doll is a sign that she has a strong desire to become a happy family housewife in the future, she dreams of being a loving parent of sweet children. In addition to raising children, she has a strong desire to work in her chosen profession and benefit society, which means that she has to work twice as hard as men. Therefore, supporting women, honoring their dreams, ensuring gender equality in society should be one of our priority goals.

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